

stages (76 DT), close correlations between average severity on a hill and the flag leaf (LAD1) or second leaf (LAD2) were observed. At all growth stages, incidence on all upper three leaves (ILT) was closely related to average severity on these leaves (ALAD).

Results suggest that BB severity can be assessed on one of the upper three leaves instead of on all three. The method could be further simplified by counting infected leaves, rather than by estimating leaf damage. □

Susceptibility of bacterial blight (BB) differential varieties of IRRI, Japan, and Korea in Nepal

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BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Xco) is a major rice disease in the terai and inner terai regions (main rice-growing area) of Nepal. Recently, this disease was observed also in the warm river basins of the hill regions. The numerous pathogenic races of Xco in Nepal hinder efforts to breed resistant varieties. To identify pathogenic variability of Xco, IRRI and Japanese varieties were tested as possible differentials at Parwanipur, Janakpur, and Kankai from 1979 to 1987.

Twenty-one-day-old seedlings of differential varieties were transplanted in 3 rows, each 5 m long. Each hill had 1 seedling and spacing was 20 × 20 cm. The plots were fertilized with NPK at 120-30-30 kg/ha. Plants were clip-inoculated at maximum tillering. The disease was scored 21 d after inoculation according to the IRRI *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

All IRRI varieties and Japanese differentials except DV85 in the 1979 test at Kankai were found susceptible to Nepalese isolates. The differential varieties have these resistance genes: Java 14, *Xa-1* and *Xa-3*; Kogyoku, *Xa-1* and *Xa-kg*; Nigeria 5, *Xa-1* and *Xa-2*; Tetep, *Xa-1* and *Xa-2*; IR20, *Xa-4*; IR1545-339-2-2, *xa-5*; DV85, *xa-5* and

Xa-7; Kuntlan, *Xa-6*; and CAS209, *Xa-10*. During 1979 tests, Korean differentials Milyang 23, Yushin, Suweon 281, and Tongil with resistance genes from Kinmaze, Kogyoku, Kogyoku, and Rantai-emas groups, respectively, were also nonfunctional against Parwanipur and Kankai isolates.

Thus, IRRI, Japanese, and Korean resistant varieties cannot be used as differentials to identify pathogenic races of Xco in Nepal. Therefore, national programs should develop their own differentials, possibly using local popular varieties, to monitor pathogenic variability of Xco. □

Insect resistance

Use of tissue culture to evaluate rice resistance to lepidopterous pests

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Larval development was evaluated on plant tissues cultured from rice genotypes varying in levels of insect resistance. Murashige and Skoog (MS) and Linsmaier and Skoog (LS) media were used to induce and develop callus. Each liter of MS medium was supplemented with 2 mg 2,4-D, 1 mg BAP, and 30 g sucrose (MS3); and each

liter of LS medium, with 1 mg 2,4-D and 30 g sucrose. *Oryza ridleyi* and Rexoro calli were obtained on LS medium; Chianan 2, Yabami Montakhab 47, and IR5865-26-1 calli were obtained on MS3 medium.

In a no-choice bioassay, about 200 mg of callus were placed in a 5-cm-diameter Gelman 7242 petri dish (see figure). Rexoro and *O. ridleyi* were susceptible and resistant checks, respectively. Due to limitations in available callus, Chianan 2 was bioassayed only against *Scirpophaga incertulas*, Yabami Montakhab 47 against *Chilo suppressalis*, and Ptb 10 and IR5685-26-1 against *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*. Insect egg masses were surface sterilized and incubated at 28 °C until eggs hatched. Callus in each petri

Lepidopterous pests reared on rice plant calli: a) *C. medinalis* larvae feeding on Ptb 10 callus; b) *S. incertulas* larva feeding on resistant *O. ridleyi* callus; c) growth of *C. medinalis* larvae on calli of *O. ridleyi* (c1), IR5865-26-1 (c2), Ptb 10 (c3), and Rexoro (c4); and d) growth of *C. suppressalis* larvae on calli of *O. ridleyi* (d1), Yabami Montakhab 47 (d2), and Rexoro (d3). IRRI, 1987-88.

dish was infested with 3 neonate larvae and incubated at 26 °C, at 12 h light/12 h darkness photoperiod. Each treatment was replicated five times.

In all cases, larvae developed normally on susceptible Rexoro. After 20 d of infestation, neonate *S. incertulas* larvae developed to 5th instar on Rexoro callus and to 3d on Chianan 2, but failed to survive on *O. ridleyi*. At 15 d after infestation, *C. suppressalis* neonate developed to 5th instar on Rexoro, to 4th on Yabami Montakhab 47, and to 2d on *O. ridleyi*. At 17 d after infestation, *C. medinalis* neonate larvae developed to 5th instar on Rexoro and Ptb 10 calli, to 4th on IR5865-26-1, and to 2d on *O. ridleyi* callus.

Results verify the use of tissue culture to investigate rice resistance to insect pests. Further work could provide plant breeders with sensitive screening tools to develop rice germplasm with better sustainable levels of insect resistance. □

Improved sources of plant resistance to yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* Walker in rice

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Dependable sources of resistance to YSB have not been available. For example, Ratna and Sashyashree, said to have moderate field resistance to YSB, have not been resistant to heavy infestation. Since 1980, we have worked to identify better donors of resistance.

In kharif 1980 and 1986, YSB broke out at heading stage in 121 late (140 d and above) cultures and varieties in 5 experiments and seed multiplication plots, resulting in whiteheads (up to 45.7%). In kharif 1982, 1983, 1985, and 1986 and rabi 1983 and 1987, 6 planned experiments involving 352 entries (including national and international YSB screening sets, named varieties of IRRI, and repeats from earlier years) were field tested. Test plants (minimum of 4 and maximum of 16 per entry) were implanted with 2-4 healthy, laboratory-laid 4-d-old egg masses of YSB per hill

YSB infestation in selected test entries in different screening trials under outbreak conditions or egg mass implantation in growing plants in the field. Cuttack, India, 1980-87.

Trial	Season and year	Details of entries	Entry	Infestation (%)	Deadhearts	Whiteheads			
1	Kharif 1980	30 late varieties ^a	Mahsuri	5.2					
			CR1010	45.7					
2	Kharif 1980	51 late cultures ^a (replicated)	CR301-3066	nil					
			Mahsuri	2.2					
			CR259-398-326-155	2.5					
			Jagannath	42.3					
3	Kharif 1980	10 late cultures ^a (replicated)	CR260-30	nil					
			CR1016	27.4					
4	Kharif 1980	10 late cultures ^a (replicated)	CR260-30	0.3					
			CR1018	21.6					
5	Kharif 1982	25 entries of IRTP YSB screening set + 11 others (replicated) ^b	IR9828-23-1	5.5					
			Ratna	22.8					
			W1263	9.2					
			CO 18	7.9					
			W1253	4.1					
			IR15723-45-3-2-2-2	4.8					
			CR317-166	8.0					
6	Rabi 1983	20 entries ^b	IR29	19.2					
			W1263		11.7	19.1			
			IR15723-45-3-2-2-2		16.1	11.6			
			IR9828-23-1		13.7	8.1			
			W1253		16.6	NF			
			GEB24		52.6	NF			
7	Kharif 1983	80 breeding lines ^b + 25 others	IR29	35.9		32.4			
			CR260-151-81-2-710	9.7					
			CR260-167-247-179	10.0					
			CR260-30	17.4					
			IR9828-23-1	25.0					
			IR15723-45-3-2-2-2	28.0					
			W1253	7.6					
			Sashyashree	77.3					
			8	Kharif 1985	60 entries of stem borer set (DRR) + 20 others ^b	RP2199-7-10-8-3	5.9		
						W1253	6.0		
						IR9828-23-1	4.3		
W1263	10.2								
9	Rabi 1986	30 released IR varieties + 20 other entries ^b	RP2069-39-3-1-4	39.5					
			IR20	19.2					
			IR58	18.9					
10	Kharif 1986	20 varieties on farm ^a	IR24	47.5					
			CR1018	28.6					
			CR260-100-11	2.3					
11	Rabi 1987	36 entries of stem borer screening, kharif 1986 (DRR) + 30 IR varieties + 15 others ^b	CR260-30	3.2					
			IR5	50.0					
			RP2199-3-3-1-6	8.8					
			IET9405 (OR437)	4.9					
			IR15723-45-3-2-2-2	4.0					
			W1253	9.3					
IR9828-23-1	10.5								
W1263	3.3								

^aYSB outbreak in field at heading. ^bYSB egg mass implantation in growing plants in field.

between 35 and 70 d after planting, and borer infestation was evaluated at 20-25 d after implantation.

Borer incidence in all 11 trials showed adequate YSB pressure on the 473 entries (see table).

CR260-30 (trial 4), W1253 (5), W1263 (5), IR9828-23-1 (5), IR15723-45-3-2-2-2 (5), and Mahsuri (2) proved consistently resistant to YSB. They are the most promising donors for use in YSB resistance breeding programs. □